

PECULIARITIES OF MASS MEDIA TERMS FORMATION IN THE UZBEK LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

It has been long investigated the use of terms in media. They are roughly divided into two categories: lexemas and unit terms. Unit terms are type of words that they are not divided into parts. Majority of them are the types words which originally used to nominations in use, but as time goes on they become terms. Some features of formation of terms will be investigated in this article.

It impossible to imagine one concept in one language. If this were true, some of the words have become widespread. As long as the words continues to be in practice, naturally some of them face up to development and consequently, the meaning that they express enlarges [Shoislomov, 1999]. Some of the become out of use with the passing time. If the semantic circle enlarges with the usage of words, they began to enter terminological system. The formation of words with affixation enlarged so far.

Especially, they are scientific, jurisdiction, media and political. As E.Mirahmedova states, they are come into practice efficiently in terms of within one language [Mirakhmedova,2008,156]. Being totally agree with this idea, we can say that every terminological system is flexible and certain models of word

formation is shaped and evolved. At the same time, this active system could probably be efficient in another language domain . For example, the affix *-gich* is very popular in scientific field, on the other hand it does not form any word in mass media.

It is necessary to state that, word formation with the way of affixation is not distributed relatively in all subjects. It all depends on the area of the language. Professor E.A.Begmatov believes that the adding *-lik* is ine the most profitable ones [Begmatov,1998,68]. It can clearly be seen in media terms such as *betaraflik*, *daxlsizlik*, *guvohlik*. It mainly forms the words from nouns and adjectives rather than other units.

There are some of the widespread suffixes that create new terms:

-li:

There is no counterpart of this ending in English language. It especially relates to adjectives.

Ehtirosli

Foydali

Ishonchli

Muvafaqqiyatli

Tegishli

-lik:

It denotes in English the suffix *-hood*.

Adekvatlik

Betaraflik

Betoblik

Birodarlik

Boylik

Fuqarolik

Homiylik

Ishsizlik

Mutanosiblik

Poraxo'rlik

Rozilik

Tushunmovchilik

Ustunlik

Yangilik

-siz:

The suffix is efficient in forming new word in terms of giving reverse meaning. It is translated in English as *non-*, *without*.

E'tiborsiz

Ishsiz

Mulksiz

Nafaqasiz

Natijasiz

Pulsiz

Qarshilksiz

Shaxssiz

Tartibsiz

Uysiz

Vijdonsiz

-ik(-gik):

This term formative adding is derived from mainly Russian language and its influence. The English language has direct ending such as *-ic(gic)*.

Byurokratik

Demokratik

Epizodik

Jurnalistik

Sotsoilogik

-kor:

Ehtiyotkor

Isyonkor

Omilkor

Paxtakor

The suffix is considered to be realia from linguistic point of view:

Tadbirkor

-dor:

During the investigations, we stated that there exists no proper equivalent.

Amaldor

Gumondor

Hukmdor

Mansabdor

Nomdor

-dosh:

The word *mate* could probably be the best replacement at this point.

Kursdosh

Qondosh

Sinfdosh

Tengdosh

Zamondosh

-la:

This suffix forms verbs in Uzbek.

Aniqlamoq

Jonlanmoq

Ta'minlamoq

Tiklanmoq

Yengillatmoq

-ayt:

Primarily the types of words created by adjectives are related to verbs. In target language it has counterpart as *-en* and *-fy*.

Kamaytirmoq
Kengaytirmoq
Ko'paytirmoq
Pasaytirmoq

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